

FORMATION AND APPLICATION OF ECONOMIC TERMS

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Abstract: This article focuses on the study of foreign languages in our country, the need to know foreign languages in economic relations, how to use economic neologisms.

Keywords: XXI century, diplomatic economic relations, terms, neologisms.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена изучению иностранных языков в нашей стране, необходимости знания иностранных языков в экономических отношениях, использованию экономических неологизмов.

Ключевые слова: XXI век, дипломатические экономические отношения, термины, неологизмы.

Today, in a period of developing science and technology all over the world, of course, the emphasis on the study of foreign languages is increasing day by day. "A clear example is the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to bring the activities of popularization of foreign language learning to a qualitatively new level in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Now knowledge of foreign languages is becoming much more necessary not only for philologists, but also for representatives of all spheres. Uzbekistan, knowledge of English and Russian along with the native language is of great help in the field of specialists and expands the study of achievements in the field. Especially in some cases, when one state is signing an economic contract with another state, or when establishing various diplomatic relations, international relations, there is a need for representatives of the field who speak foreign languages. It is known that the economy plays an important role in any society. Therefore, words and terms related to economics should be clear, concise and logically based. The rapid development of Science and technology does not remain without its influence on the field of economics either, as a result of which it leads to the emergence of new neologisms in the field of several more economies. There are many aspects to consider when adopting international economic words in general into Uzbek. When an economic term is entering the Uzbek language, it will be necessary to pay attention to the following aspects: to the suitability of the term for the sound system of the Uzbek language; whether it has an Uzbek alternative; to the kalka or the need to translate; to the content of the economic term; to its simplicity and fluency; to its essence and decadence.

Economic terms entering the Uzbek language from other languages must first pass through the discussion of specialists and adjectives, and then be approved from the relevant committee of the Supreme Assembly. Only then do such economic terms come into legal force and can be applied freely. Our country is gradually moving towards a market economy after independence. The laws of the market economy are being introduced in society. Neologisms serving the market economy are increasing further. A certain part of this is being uzbekized on the basis of the capabilities of our native language, and a certain part is being used as an international assimilation. In the use of economic terms in the Uzbek language, the following cases can be observed: 1. Many terms are uzbekized on the basis of the capabilities of our language. In this case, a group of terms is given with ready-made alternatives to Uzbek, a certain part is translated and used, and a part is made on the basis of the laws of the Uzbek language. For example: auction-auction, makler-dallol, kommersant-merchant, commissionnie voznagrajdeniya-mediation fee, economiceconomics, chek na pred'yavitelya-white check, impersonal check, shareholder-shareholder, businessman-businessman, etc. 2. Another way is to assimilate the international terms used in most countries of the world into Uzbek as well. In this regard, it is necessary to note that it is difficult to find an Uzbek alternative to all incoming terms. Therefore, the main part of them is used in one form in the languages of most countries of the world, and this application is convenient for information exchange of world businessmen. For example: corruption, credit, export, grant, auditor, avizo, currency, leasing, manager, license, businessman, non-resident. Below are a few terms that are widely used in the field of Economics. Some of them are Uzbek words, and some are being used in our language by entering directly from other languages.

Advertisement - (fr.reclame) is unbiased information about a good or service provided, conveying their properties, preferences, and terms of purchase to customers for the purpose of selling them more. R. it is carried out through special firms and is a high source of income.

Auction - (lat.auction) - auction, open sale. This sales service buys the product from the buyer who raises it to the highest price.

Bank - a credit and financial institution that collects and continuously circulates funds depending on the time of legal entities and individuals, performs transactions related to the currency of the Golden vachet el, intermediates in the work fee and other settlement of the parties, is made on credit, suda for verification of enterprises and money in general. B. paying the depositors a percentage of the information charges the lender a fixed interest rate, and there is a bank profit that differs in these percentages.

Business - (English business-work, activity, training) - work, activity aimed at earning wealth, profit. Business is divided into large, medium and small types,

depending on the scope of Business Administration. It is distinguished depending on the average number of employees and the size of the product.

A businessman - (English business-ism, man - man) is a person engaged in business, corchalon.

Exchange - (goll.beurs, nem. Borse-wallet) - 1) an organization that actively participates in the exchange of products, currency and securities, the implementation of accounting and information services. It receives an intermediary levy for its service; 2) the place where the exchange will be traded.

Broker - (Eng.broker) - official dallol between products, Securities, currency sellers and buyers. A person who has the right to make agreements, contracts on his own or on behalf of clients.

Currency - (ital. valuta. lat. valere-to be appreciated, value)- means of payment equated to the monetary unit of the country and its type (gold, silver, paper, money).

Veksel - (nem.Wechsel, exactly-exchange) - a valuable paper of a special appearance issued in writing on debt obligations. the lender has the right to demand the loan at the end of the period specified in the bill.

Import - (lat.importo-I will enter) - 1) foreign products imported for use or sale into the country; 2) capital I.- capital coming from abroad to the country (credit, bonds and other); 3) the total number and value of imported products.

Investment - (nem.investiture, lat. investere-dress) - invest capital funds for the implementation of an activity by an investor, for the purpose of introducing investments, making a profit. I. it can be carried out within the country (domestic investment) and in foreign countries (foreign investment). Finance I.si-includes purchases of securities, savings of funds, etc., investments in real material production.

Mortgage - (Greek.hypothek-collateral)-foreclosure of a certain real estate (land, castle, etc.) in order to obtain a loan, loan.

License - (lat.licentia-freedom, right)- a permit; 1) a permit issued by state bodies to bring goods from foreign countries or to issue goods abroad; 2) the right to use something with or without light conditions; 3) a reduction in duty fees when issuing goods or entering goods from the border. Patented L.- to give to others the right to use the discovery, which is registered and issued a certificate.

Patent - (lat. patens-certificate, label)- 1) A certificate that allows you to engage in some type of entrepreneurship in a private way, issued by financial authorities on the basis of relevant documents; 2) A certificate confirming authorship of scientific discovery and invention. P. patented by the state.

Polis - (fr.police, ital, pollissa-tilkhat)-a document on the conclusion of a personal or property insurance contract and its conditions.

Certificate - (fr.certificate - I confirm, I testify) is a document that testifies. For example: auditor's certificate - a document confirming the correctness of the balance

sheet of the declared firm. An insurance certificate is a document in which the terms of the insurance contract are recorded. A certificate of equity is a document confirming that its owner owns part of the capital of the society (company). Certificate of commodity quality in foreign economic relations, etc.k.

As a result of the improvement of the mechanisms of the market economy in our country, all forms of private ownership are developing and a wide path is being opened to entrepreneurial activity, in Natja, buying and selling with foreign countries, that is, exportimport work is carried out, in this regard, knowledge of a foreign language is very important, in particular, understanding economic neologisms In this regard, the first Prezdent of our Republic I.A.Let us recall Karimov's speech:”the service of a foreign language is great in the preparation of a wide range of National Personnel of the world, comprehensively competent, worldview, who have received knowledge of the level of World templates for the implementation of socio-political, spiritual and economic reforms of our country.”

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